

Effects of Covid-19 pandemic on female academicians' psychological state in Lithuanian HEIs and RPOs

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Purpose

The striking fact: among other occupational groups, academics rank among those with the highest levels of common mental disorders: the prevalence of common psychological disorders estimated to be between 32% and 42% among academic employees and postgraduate students, compared to approximately 19% in the general population (Kismihók et al., 2021). It can be assumed that the numbers are even higher among academic women as some studies report that women in full-time employment are nearly twice as likely to have a common mental health problem as full-time employed men (19,8% vs 10,9%) (Mental health Foundation).

Moreover, vulnerabilities, which may cause psychological disorders, have been experienced regardless of the stage of career, both among PhD students (Quijada, 2021; Woolston, 2019) and senior faculty (Lashuel, 2020; Bira et al., 2019). Significant transformations of personal and academic lives that were caused by the Covid-19 pandemic to almost all employees in research institutions even strengthened the vulnerabilities of academics (Watermeyer et al., 2021).

Furthermore, number of studies report that the Covid-19 pandemic had strong negative effects on women's lives in many countries (e.g. Alon et al., 2020; Oertelt-Prigione 2020; UN 2020). Also, the studies report that women were among those for whom the Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown was particularly stressful (Christoph et al., 2020). These findings are indicative of women's vulnerability in academic environments (e.g. Bonanomi et al., 2021; Oleschuk, 2020; Ribarovskaa et al., 2021; Shalaby et al., 2021; Shen & Slater, 2021). Thus, extending this line of the studies, the paper aims to reflect on the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic related restrictions on psychological wellbeing of female academics and related institutional contexts in HEIs and RPOs in Lithuania.

The context: Research and gender in Lithuania

Lithuania is a small country with up to 3 mln. citizens and with 53% of women among them (Official Statistics Portal, 2020). As EIGE Gender Equality Index indicates, 52% of women and 62% of men were in full time employment positions and 23% of women and 17% of men were at-risk-of-poverty in 2021. Furthermore, 79% of women and 29% of men were doing cooking and/or household every day and 41% of women and 24% of men were caring for and educating their children or grandchildren, elderly or people with disabilities every day in the same year. On the other hand, 19% of women and 81% of men were members of boards in largest quoted companies, supervisory board or board of directors (EIGE, 2021).

Ministry of Education, Science and Sport leads the national science system. The system encompasses 2 national funding institutions – The Research Council of Lithuania and the Agency for Science, Innovation and Technology – and 20 HEIs (public and private) and 14 research institutes (public and private) (AIKOS, 2022). The R&D expenditure, compared to GDP, was 0,9% in 2017 and increased to 1,7% in 2020 (Official Statistics Portal, 2022).

In 2018, before the pandemic, 12036 persons were employed in HEIs. The number slightly decreased up to 11495 in 2019, the year then the pandemic started, and was 11777 in 2021. During the period, proportion of women was almost stable – 55-56% – among the employed in HEIs (Official Statistics Portal, 2022).

The study design

In this paper, we present small part of findings of a web-based national questionnaire survey (n=891) that was carried out among women who were working in HEIs and RPOs in Lithuania in summer 2021 (Paliokaitė et al., 2022). The survey was carried out using the Alchemer application. The questionnaire was developed based on the GEAR tool methodology (ACT, 2020) and included 7 sets of questions covering such topics as gender stereotypes, gender equality in organizational cultures, institutional measures focused on gender equality, women's leadership and effects of restrictions related to the Covid-19 pandemic. The last topic was measured by 15 statements in a Likert scale ranging from 1 (“totally disagree”) and 7 (“totally agree”). The statements denoted both positive (e.g. *“I had more time for writing papers”*) and negative (e.g. *“I had/have less time for research”*) effects of the pandemic on personal life (e.g. *“Other family members and/or close people took over part of my caring or housework*

commitments”), and institutional dependence (e.g. “*The institution that I work for provided me with sufficient support*”). Additionally, the respondents were asked to comment their evaluations providing their personal examples.

Further in this paper we focus on the respondents’ self-evaluation of change in psychological state (the statement “*My psychological state has worsened*”) as an outcome of the Covid-19 lockdown and related changes in personal life and work environments as evaluated by particular statements and individual comments. In addition, we compare evaluations of the respondents who had PhD and were PhD students.

The analysis of the responses was carried out with the SPSS 23.0 software. It included descriptive statistics, analysis of correlation (Pearson’s R) and linear regression (a stepwise method).

Results

50,2% of the respondents reported that they (absolutely) agree or more agree than disagree with the statement “*my psychological state has worsened*” because of restrictions related to the Covid-19 pandemic. The percentage slightly varies among respondents who already had PhD (48,2%) and were PhD students (52,5%) (Table 1).

Analysis of correlation (Table 2) shows that the self-evaluation of change in psychological state strongly interrelates with self-evaluation of change in physical condition ($R_p=0,699$ $p<0,01$), with a feeling that on-line teaching was/still is difficult psychologically ($R_p=0,574$ $p<0,01$) and a feeling that remote working was/still is difficult physically ($R_p=0,547$ $p<0,01$). Although other correlations are weaker (e.g. $R_p=$ from $-0,272$ to $0,474$ $p<0,01$), they suggest that the change in one’s psychological state relates to many other aspects of personal life (e.g. increased family responsibilities) and work (e.g. postponed career advancement), including institutional efforts to ensure wellbeing of employees. More specifically, the less time the respondents had for accomplishing their research, the more significantly the respondents’ productivity decreased, and the more the respondents’ responsibilities for their families / intimates increased, the more the respondents’ psychological state has worsened ($R_p=$ from $0,300$ to $0,474$ $p<0,01$).

Contrarily, more time for writing research papers and increased possibilities to participate in international research activities as well as institutional efforts to provide psychological assistance and information and support necessary for adaptation to requirements of remote

working appear as factors, which positively contribute to respondents' psychological state during the pandemic. I.e. evaluations of the above mentioned factors negatively correlate with the evaluation of worsening of the psychological state (R_P from $-0,272$ to $-0,150$ $p < 0,01$).

Linear regression analysis (Table 3) shows that several factors predetermine ($R^2_{Adj}=0,685$) the self-evaluation of change in the state: deterioration of physical condition ($B=0,650$); on-line teaching was/still is emotionally difficult ($B=0,201$); significant decrease in personal productivity ($B=0,138$). In addition, the regression analysis suggests that the models of the worsening state predetermining factors slightly differ in populations of PhDs and PhD students, and have stronger explanatory power in the last one (respectively, $R^2_{Adj}=0,669$ and $R^2_{Adj}=0,896$). The perception of a worsening physical condition was a significant factor predetermining worsening of psychological state in both populations ($B_{PhD}=0,765$ and $B_{PhDstudents}=0,928$). However, for PhD students, more time for writing research papers also contributed to improving their psychological state ($B=-0,214$). Meanwhile for the PhDs, in addition to worsened physical condition, emotional difficulty of teaching on-line ($B=0,289$), significant decrease in productivity ($B=0,099$), and postponed promotions ($B=0,093$) contributed to worsening of the state.

The regression analysis did not yield any institutional factors – i.e. the amount of information and support necessary for adaptation to online work, which was provided by the institution; the amount of institutional efforts striving to personalize the work place at home; sufficiency of psychological support provided by the institution – as affecting self-evaluation of change in psychological state. In general, more than half of the respondents (52,4%) agreed that their employers provided sufficient information and support for them to adapt to remote working in the form of training, and respective consultations (e.g. digital tools for work). However, just 20% of the respondents agreed that their employers provided help with the equipment to make the necessary adjustment for work from home or provided psychological counselling (Table 1).

Comments to the statements indicate that some academic institutions made very few attempts (e.g. released regulations for remote working) or none to help their employees to adapt to the changed working conditions. A case was mentioned when the employer even threatened their employees that if they do not adapt to the change in the working mode, the employer will terminate contracts. The Research Council of Lithuania decided that the pandemic does not restrict the possibility to perform research and amendments to the contracts of research projects were not made. Personal and family resources were relied heavily in these conditions, e.g.

upgrading the equipment, internet connection and software. This contrasted with the different working conditions created for some respondents' spouses by private enterprises as employers. Improving the equipment would not have been a problem if salaries in the sector were higher.

Among the positive effects a quarter of the respondents totally agreed with the statement that the pandemic provided them with more opportunities to participate in international research events, and a third had more time to write academic papers. Comments from the survey state that some women in academia considered the pandemic period as the best in their career because of the flexible work schedule, free laboratories, more leisure time, possibility for self-reflection; some women got equipment for remote working for the first time in their working life.

Implications

The study findings augment previous reports on worsened psychological wellbeing of academic female employees during the Covid-19 pandemic (e.g. Pieha et al., 2020). More than half of the respondents reported that their psychological state worsened because of restrictions related to the Covid-19 pandemic and the worsening was strongly predetermined by worsening of the physical condition. Furthermore, emotional difficulties related to on-line teaching and remote working, less time for writing research papers and decreased productivity, postponed promotions contributed negatively to worsening of the psychological state. Meanwhile more time for writing research papers, psychological and informative support from the institutions were positively related with change in the psychological state.

Furthermore, effects of the Covid-19 pandemic-related restrictions on the respondents' psychological state slightly varied comparing the respondents with PhD and PhD students. More specifically, more than half (52,5%) of the female PhD students who participated in the survey reported that their psychological state worsened because of restrictions related to the Covid-19 pandemic; the percentage was slightly lower among respondents who already had PhD (48,2%). Worsened physical condition had significant negative effect on psychological state in both populations, but on-line teaching related emotional difficulties, significantly decreased productivity and postponed promotion had stronger negative effects on psychological state in the population of women holding the PhD. Meanwhile emerged time for research paper writing had additional but positive effect on the state in the PhD students' population.

Thus, the findings reveal peculiarities of the pandemic effects on two categories of the academic employees – i.e. PhDs and PhD students – and, correspondingly, suggest several lines of possible institutional interventions. Importantly, a proper physical condition of the employees is important to ensure psychological wellbeing. This could be achieved by purposive education, targeted measures (e.g. trainings, collective exercising) and implementing the policies (e.g. providing ergonomic equipment in work and home working spaces). This is in line with recommendations from prior research findings on the importance of suitability and adjustment of the working environment for productivity and wellbeing (Karabulut, 2022; Rossi, 2021). In addition, particular attention should be given to issues arising from the remote working and on-line teaching. Specific trainings, flexible schedules could be part of resolutions. Finally, institutions should take responsibility for not only requiring research results, but also taking into consideration other duties and responsibilities of their diverse employees as suggested by researchers in gender studies (e.g. Utoft, 2020) as well as research integrity (e.g. Mejlgaard et al., 2020). This requires changes at national level, redefining merits in the assessment and reward processes to promote cooperation, mentoring, networking, social impact activities and teaching.

Finally, referring to other studies on the topic, further qualitative studies on the psychological wellbeing of female academic workers during critical periods could contribute to identification of the challenges associated with working from home and offer solutions (Okuyan and Begen, 2021), the ways of constructing a sense of social belonging, connectedness to a (professional, work) community and trust, the ways of ensuring spontaneous socializability and building trust in hybrid teams. In addition, quantitative studies with samples of senior faculty may help to better understand the impact of mental wellbeing (differentiating it from work wellbeing) on work-ability, and the role of self-compassion and mindfulness as a mediator.

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Table 1. Descriptive Statistics: Average evaluations of Covid-19 effects.

	All respondents			PhD			PhD student			No (striving for) PhD		
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. Had / have more time for writing research papers	647	3,57	2,034	423	3,51	2,044	98	3,53	1,949	112	3,86	2,088
2. Had / have less time for accomplishing my research investigations	640	4,86	1,840	420	4,95	1,851	93	4,31	1,769	114	4,91	1,822
3. It was impossible to accomplish planned research (e.g. closed laboratories, possibility to reach research participants)	579	4,18	1,969	380	4,22	1,995	77	4,03	1,739	110	4,05	2,036
4. Had more possibilities to participate in international research activities (e.g. conferences, trainings, networking)	662	3,97	1,896	424	3,90	1,881	111	4,32	1,927	113	3,90	1,932
5. My productivity decreased significantly	708	3,94	1,890	425	3,91	1,885	152	3,81	1,911	116	4,12	1,884
6. My family members and / or intimates took over part of my caring and / or housekeeping responsibilities	620	3,14	1,734	377	3,02	1,743	129	3,36	1,758	100	3,21	1,671
7. My responsibilities for the family and / or intimates increased so much that prevented my professional activities	659	3,56	1,933	399	3,67	1,977	142	3,25	1,873	103	3,57	1,818
8. Teaching on-line was / is difficulty emotionally	543	4,40	1,907	363	4,44	1,865	89	4,18	1,969	78	4,38	2,078
9. Remote working was / is difficult physically	682	3,71	1,887	417	3,78	1,912	143	3,37	1,806	108	3,77	1,883
10. My psychological wellbeing has worsened	718	4,21	1,889	426	4,12	1,861	160	4,19	1,912	116	4,46	2,010
11. My physical condition has worsened	718	4,22	1,903	426	4,12	1,904	160	4,19	1,891	116	4,54	1,913
12. My promotion was postponed	409	2,45	1,622	268	2,50	1,682	75	2,20	1,356	56	2,55	1,662
13. My research and study institution where I work provided me with sufficient psychological assistance (e.g. support, psychological consultations, etc.)	550	3,33	1,874	336	3,21	1,835	120	3,85	1,930	84	3,13	1,868
14. The research and study institution where I work provided enough information and support for me to adopt to requirements of remote working (e.g. trainings, consultations, etc.)	666	4,61	1,893	405	4,66	1,923	145	4,77	1,807	103	4,21	1,877
15. The research and study institution where I work has made sure that my workplace at home is adapted to my direct work (e.g. made it possible to use a work computer at home, provided other facilities)	648	3,38	2,058	401	3,35	2,054	138	3,63	2,172	97	3,14	1,963

Table 2. Analysis of correlation: Interrelations between the self-evaluation of change in psychological state and other effects of Covid-19 pandemic.

		10. My psychological state has worsened			
		All sample	PhD	PhD student	No (striving for) PhD
1. Had / have more time for writing research papers	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-,272** 0,000 642	-,280** 0,000 419	-,316** 0,002 98	-,265** 0,005 111
2. Had / have less time for accomplishing my research investigations	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	,300** 0,000 636	,290** 0,000 416	,212* 0,041 93	,408** 0,000 114
3. It was impossible to accomplish planned research (e.g. closed laboratories, possibility to reach research participants)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	,247** 0,000 574	,293** 0,000 376	0,162 0,160 77	0,145 0,132 109
4. Had more possibilities to participate in international research activities (e.g. conferences, trainings, networking)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-,138** 0,000 657	-,138** 0,005 420	-0,183 0,054 111	-0,112 0,240 112
5. My productivity decreased significantly	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	,474** 0,000 704	,478** 0,000 422	,390** 0,000 152	,557** 0,000 115
6. My family members and / or intimates took over part of my caring and / or housekeeping responsibilities	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	0,022 0,579 617	0,054 0,298 375	-0,025 0,778 129	-0,025 0,808 99
7. My responsibilities for the family and / or intimates increased so much that prevented my professional activities	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	,326** 0,000 657	,405** 0,000 397	0,156 0,065 142	,276** 0,005 103
8. Teaching on-line was / is difficulty emotionally	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	,574** 0,000 541	,590** 0,000 362	,613** 0,000 89	,492** 0,000 77
9. Remote working was / is difficult physically	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	,547** 0,000 679	,577** 0,000 415	,506** 0,000 143	,507** 0,000 107
11. My physical condition has worsened	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	,699** 0,000 716	,710** 0,000 425	,645** 0,000 159	,733** 0,000 116
12. My promotion was postponed	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	,276** 0,000 407	,288** 0,000 267	,337** 0,003 75	0,238 0,080 55
13. My research and study institution where I work provided me with sufficient psychological assistance (e.g. support, psychological consultations, etc.)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-,217** 0,000 547	-,182** 0,001 334	-,283** 0,002 120	-,292** 0,007 83
14. The research and study institution where I work provided enough information and support for me to adopt to requirements of remote working (e.g. trainings, consultations, etc.)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-,150** 0,000 663	-,100* 0,045 403	-,221** 0,008 145	-,228* 0,021 102
15. The research and study institution where I work has made sure that my workplace at home is adapted to my direct work (e.g. made it possible to use a work computer at home, provided other facilities)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-0,026 0,503 644	-0,042 0,404 399	-0,001 0,988 137	0,033 0,749 96

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 3. Linear regression analysis: Factors predetermining worsening in psychological wellbeing e (R2Adj=0,685) the self-evaluation of change in the wellbeing.

Dependent Variable: 10. My psychological wellbeing has worsened

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,794 ^a	,631	,629	1,108
2	,821 ^b	,673	,671	1,045
3	,830 ^c	,689	,685	1,022

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,969	,180		5,383	,000
	11. My physical condition has worsened	,771	,037	,794	20,579	,000
2	(Constant)	,419	,195		2,143	,033
	11. My physical condition has worsened	,673	,039	,693	17,127	,000
	8. Teaching on-line was / is difficulty emotionally	,224	,039	,230	5,674	,000
3	(Constant)	,160	,205		,779	,437
	11. My physical condition has worsened	,631	,040	,650	15,678	,000
	8. Teaching on-line was / is difficulty emotionally	,196	,039	,201	4,971	,000
	5. My productivity decreased significantly	,137	,039	,138	3,482	,001

Model Summary					
	Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
PhD	1	,765 ^b	,586	,584	1,170
	2	,811 ^c	,657	,653	1,067
	3	,818 ^d	,668	,663	1,053
	4	,822 ^e	,676	,669	1,043
PhD student	1	,928 ^b	,862	,858	,624
	2	,950 ^f	,902	,896	,535
No (striving for) PhD	1	,851 ^b	,723	,714	1,085
	2	,890 ^g	,792	,778	,956

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
PhD	1	(Constant)	1,104	,218		5,066	,000
		11. My physical condition has worsened	,736	,047	,765	15,783	,000
	2	(Constant)	,431	,228		1,890	,060
		11. My physical condition has worsened	,591	,049	,615	12,105	,000
		8. Teaching on-line was / is difficulty emotionally	,294	,049	,306	6,028	,000
	3	(Constant)	,201	,244		,824	,411
		11. My physical condition has worsened	,567	,049	,590	11,544	,000
		8. Teaching on-line was / is difficulty emotionally	,299	,048	,312	6,214	,000
		12. My promotion was postponed	,116	,048	,108	2,420	,017
	4	(Constant)	,033	,255		,128	,899
		5. My productivity decreased significantly	,098	,048	,099	2,063	,041
		11. My physical condition has worsened	,546	,050	,568	10,969	,000
	8. Teaching on-line was / is difficulty emotionally	,277	,049	,289	5,672	,000	
	12. My promotion was postponed	,100	,048	,093	2,074	,040	
PhD student	1	(Constant)	,693	,314		2,210	,035
		11. My physical condition has worsened	,866	,062	,928	13,915	,000
	2	(Constant)	1,646	,382		4,306	,000
		11. My physical condition has worsened	,794	,057	,851	13,906	,000
	1. Had / have more time for writing research papers	-,187	,054	-,214	-3,503	,001	
No (striving for) PhD	1	(Constant)	,258	,537		,481	,634
		11. My physical condition has worsened	,925	,106	,851	8,710	,000
	2	(Constant)	-1,291	,694		-1,861	,073
		11. My physical condition has worsened	,836	,098	,769	8,529	,000
		2. Had / have less time for accomplishing my research investigations	,384	,126	,275	3,053	,005